

Boiled Cassava Food Target Product Profile Workplan, at NaCRRI-Uganda

Kampala, Uganda, October 2025

Enock WEMBABAZI, NaCRRI, Uganda

Alfred OSIMATI, NaCRRI, Uganda

Paula IRAGABA, NaCRRI, Uganda

Williams ESUMA, NaCRRI, Uganda

This report has been written in the framework of the RTBfoodomics project (under CIRAD coordination), as a continuation of work initiated under the RTBfoods and RTB Breeding projects.

To be cited as:

Enock WEMBABAZI, Alfred OSIMATI, Paula IRAGABA, Williams ESUMA (2025). *Boiled Cassava Food Target Product Profile Workplan, at NaCRRRI-Uganda.* Namulongue, Uganda: RTBfoodomics, Institute Roadmap, 11p. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17610239>.

Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the RTBfoodomics, through a grant from the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF) to the French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development (CIRAD), Montpellier, France, incorporated in the grant agreement INV-054662_2024 between CIRAD and BMGF.

Image cover page © CIRAD.

This document has been reviewed by	
Dominique DUFOUR Royal Holloway University Team	Quarter 2, 2025 Quarter 2, 2025
Final validation by	
Hernan CEBALLOS	Quarter 2, 2025

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Table of Figures	4
Abstract	5
1 Phenotyping samples.....	6
1.1 Phenotyping using harmonized SOPs: Core traits	6
1.2 Phenotyping for aroma and flavor	6
1.3 Additional traits to phenotype	6
2 Definition of genotypes to screen.	6
2.1 Alternative back-up germplasm or sources of sampling.....	8
3 Sampling strategy and experimental design.....	8
3.1 Schematic description of sample processing and handling.....	8
3.2 Replication	8
3.3 Sensory evaluation of collected samples	9
4 Chronogram of activities.....	9
Appendice.....	11
RHUL team feedback	11

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Workflow for conducting sensory evaluation on cassava	6
Figure 2: Illustration of proposed key steps in sample preparation, processing and shipment of cassava for NaCRRRI	9
Table 1: Mealiness data for cassava released varieties, advanced breeding lines and landraces for Population 1	7
Table 2: Summary of the 15 genotypes to screen (phenotype for mealiness and for metabolomic studies) ..	7
Table 3: Tentative chronogram of activities.....	10

ABSTRACT

The RTBfoodomics project officially started with a kickoff and planning meeting organized at CIAT (Cali, Colombia) in March 2025. This gathering brought together the partners of the project to align on project activities and responsibilities. Defining a standard sampling protocol was of particular importance.

Following the meeting, NaCRRI produced a detailed workplan outlining the genotypes to be harvested and the samples to be produced and analyzed. The sampling protocol was discussed at length to ensure enough replications of each genotype were included in the workplans (at planting, harvesting and sample preparation).

NaCRRI-Uganda strategy for phenotyping cassava genotypes will focus on mealiness, the core trait for boiled cassava. A trained sensory panel at NaCRRI will evaluate mealiness, aroma, and additional traits such as softness, smoothness, stickiness, sweetness, bitterness, and moldability using standardized protocols. The study involves two genotype sets: one from a germplasm conservation trial of 50 diverse genotypes, including popular landraces and released varieties, and another from an Advanced Yield Trial (AYT) of 20 elite clones. From these, 15 contrasting genotypes will be selected for metabolomic analysis.

Sampling involves harvesting six plants per genotype, selecting two healthy roots per plant, and dividing them into raw and boiled halves. Samples are freeze-dried following detailed protocols and shipped to RHUL for metabolomic profiling. Sensory evaluation is conducted on the boiled halves to assess mealiness. The AYT trial is replicated, while the germplasm trial is not. Each harvested plant serves as a biological replicate. The workplan ensures sufficient root material and includes backup genotypes if needed. A detailed chronogram integrates planting, harvesting, processing, and shipment timelines to support the successful execution of the study.

Key Words: Cassava, Mealiness, Sensory panel, Phenotyping, Genotype selection, Metabolomics, Freeze-drying, Landraces, Advanced Yield Trial (AYT), Sample processing

1 PHENOTYPING SAMPLES

1.1 Phenotyping using harmonized SOPs: Core traits

Cassava root mealiness: The core trait for boiled cassava root at NaCRRRI is mealiness. Mealiness of root samples will be assessed using a trained sensory panel (~12 panelists) at NaCRRRI, Namulonge (**Figure 1**). Twelve marketable cassava roots will be harvested from 6 plants in each plot and collated. The roots will be washed with clean water, peeled, sectioned, cooked for 55 minutes and then profiled for mealiness according to the SOP for sensory characterization of boiled cassava (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00599>).

Figure 1: Workflow for conducting sensory evaluation on cassava

1.2 Phenotyping for aroma and flavor

Aroma will be assessed on cooked root samples using a trained sensory panel according to an established SOP (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00599>).

1.3 Additional traits to phenotype

- Softness (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00599>)
- Smoothness (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00599>)
- Stickiness (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00599>)
- Sweetness (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00599>)
- Bitterness (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00599>)
- Moldability (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00599>)

2 DEFINITION OF GENOTYPES TO SCREEN.

The genetic materials from which contrasting genotypes will finally be selected have two kinds of origins. The first set of germplasm includes a group of **eight** selected popular landraces, released varieties, and elite clones from the breeding program and will form part of the panel for metabolomic analysis. This set includes NAROCASS 1 (moderately mealy), NASE 14 (highly mealy) and NASE 3 (low mealiness) which have been previously profiled for mealiness (**Table 1**). These have been replanted in a germplasm conservation trial at NaCRRRI in Namulonge and are ready for harvesting (**Table 2**). This trial consists of a total of 50 genotypes including released varieties, land races and advanced breeding lines. The landraces were included to capture mealiness preferences of boiled cassava consumers.

Table 1: Mealiness data for cassava released varieties, advanced breeding lines and landraces for Population 1

Genotype	Type of Material	Mealiness QDA	Class
Alado Alado	Landrace	7.90	High
NASE14	Improved	9.08	High
TME14	Improved	6.82	Moderate
UG120193	Advanced	6.50	Moderate
NAROCASS 1	Improved	6.84	Moderate
BUKALASA	Landrace	6.55	Moderate
MKUMBA	Advanced	3.17	Low
NASE 3	Improved	3.42	Low

Table 2: Summary of the 15 genotypes to screen (phenotype for mealiness and for metabolomic studies).

Six plants per repetition were planted on April 2024 in Namulonge and will be harvested in May 2025.

Genotype Category	Genotype	Phenotypic score		Number of reps
		Trait 1	Trait 2	
Released	NAROCASS 1	6.84	Extrusion texture	1
Released	NASE14	9.08	Extrusion texture	1
Released	NASE3	3.42	Extrusion texture	1
Advanced breeding line	TME14	6.82	Extrusion texture	1
Advanced breeding line	UG120193	6.50	Extrusion texture	1
Advanced breeding line	MKUMBA	3.17	Extrusion texture	1
Landrace	Bukalasa	6.55	Extrusion texture	1
Landrace	Alado Alado	7.55	Extrusion texture	1
Advanced breeding line	AYT_clone1	TBD	Extrusion texture	2
Advanced breeding line	AYT_clone2	TBD	Extrusion texture	2
Advanced breeding line	AYT_clone3	TBD	Extrusion texture	2
Advanced breeding line	AYT_clone4	TBD	Extrusion texture	2
Advanced breeding line	AYT_clone5	TBD	Extrusion texture	2
Advanced breeding line	AYT_clone6	TBD	Extrusion texture	2
Advanced breeding line	AYT_clone7	TBD	Extrusion texture	2

TBD= to be defined

The second set of genotypes originate from an Advanced Yield Trial (AYT) panel planted at NaCRRRI in April 2024 (<https://www.cassavabase.org/breeders/trial/18343?format=>). They will be used to select genotypes that offer suitable phenotypic variability. The population is constituted by 20 elite clones from different full-sib families that were extracted from the genomic selection cycle three population improvement scheme currently in AYT. These clones form a set of candidates for advancement to Uniform Yield Trials (UYT) and potential release as varieties. They will be subjected to QDA for identification of seven contrasting genotypes for mealiness to complete the 15 required contrasting genotypes for metabolomic analysis.

2.1 Alternative back-up germplasm or sources of sampling

The germplasm conservation trial has 50 diverse genotypes with a plot size of 64 plants. Therefore, we anticipate to have enough root material from each genotype. In the event that the selected genotypes do not meet the root requirements, other genotypes in the trial will be considered.

3 SAMPLING STRATEGY AND EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

3.1 Schematic description of sample processing and handling

Six plants per genotype will be harvested and then two mid-sized, healthy roots will be selected from each plant as described in section 1.1. Roots are then partitioned into two longitudinal half portions. The first portion will be boiled whereas the second will be maintained raw and then freeze dried (**Figure 2**). A small sample from each of the two boiled halves will be taken, homogenized and freeze dried. The rest of the boiled halves will be pooled together for a sensory panel to assess mealiness. Freeze-dried samples will be shipped to RHUL for metabolomic profiling. Sample preparation for freeze-drying will be done according to Alamu et al (2023):

1. Cut off proximal and distal ends of the root to retain a middle portion that depicts common practice among consumers
2. For raw sample, cut the root longitudinally into halves and leave one half for freeze drying as raw sample and the other for sensory testing and freeze drying after cooking
3. To process raw freeze-dried sample, cut the root portions into small slices and thoroughly mix to achieve a homogeneous sample
4. Load the samples into labelled polyethylene bags and place them into the freeze-drier.
5. For boiled samples, the raw roots will be cooked following the *Sensory Characterization of Boiled Cassava* SOP (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00599>).
6. After cooking, samples will be mashed then loaded into a freeze-drier.
7. Freeze drying of both sample sets will be done according to Alamu et al (2023); DOI 10.3389/fsufs.2023.1129779.
8. Freeze-dried samples will be stored in labelled zip lock bags for shipping to RHUL.

3.2 Replication

The AYT trial has been replicated twice in the field whereas the germplasm conservation trial is not replicated (**Table 2**). For AYT materials, 3 plants will be harvested from each of the two replications (six plants in total), whereas for the popular varieties, all six plants will be harvested from the single available replication. Each harvested plant serves as a biological replicate. Two roots will be selected from each harvested plant (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2: Illustration of proposed key steps in sample preparation, processing and shipment of cassava for NaCRR

Six plants will be harvested from each genotype. Two (mid-size and healthy) roots per plant are selected. Roots are cut longitudinally into two halves. One (uncooked) half is used as raw sample. The other half is boiled. Small cubes from each boiled half are extracted, homogenized and freeze-dried. The rest of the boiled halves are then used for a sensory panel.

3.3 Sensory evaluation of collected samples

Sensory evaluation will be as described in Section 1.1 and Figure 2 to aid selection of additional genotypes that constitute the fifteen diverse types for mealiness.

4 CHRONOGRAM OF ACTIVITIES

Information in Table 1 and Figure 1 regarding dates of planting, harvesting, processing and sample shipment can then be integrated into a chronogram of activities through the shipment of samples to the RHUL lab

Table 3: Tentative chronogram of activities

Field		Sensory panel	Sample shipment		
Planting	Harvest	All clones		Frozen (CIRAD)	Freeze-dried (RHUL)
April 2024	May 2025	28/04/2025 through 02/05/2025	28/04/2025 through 02/05/2025	NA	26/05/2025 through 30/05/2025

APPENDICE

RHUL team feedback

Experimental design and planning are compliant with metabolomics guidelines defined in the project although some points need clarity (please see comments). Very much appreciated the efforts in adapting methodology and sampling for metabolomics analysis and looking forward to analysing the sample set.

Please find comments below:

Q1: please indicate in the title the food product that will be targeted. My understanding is Boiled Cassava, but please indicate if otherwise.

Q2: If boiled cassava is the FPHP defined the phenotyping SOPs in sections 1.2 (aroma, flavour) and 1.3 (additional) are not relevant except for softness. Will WAB30 measurement be included too? Phenotyping sections 1.2 and 1.3 seem to be more relevant for Fufu and/or Gari/Eba, hence our questions.

Q3: The description and selection of genotypes is a bit unclear. Could you please confirm/clarify if I understand correctly the following?:

There are 2 sets of germplasm available:

Set 1 represented in Table 2, there are only 15 genotypes but text indicates a total of 50 genotypes. Does this mean that only the 15 genotypes (out of 50) included in the table will be selected for phenotyping and metabolomics? Otherwise, please provide the full list of 50 genotypes.

Set 2, representing the AYT panel comprising 20 elite clones from different biparental (full-sib) families selected from GS cycle. Is this Set 2 the contingency/alternative back-up germplasm? Will additional 15 genotypes from this set 2 panel also selected (based on QDA scores) for metabolomics too?

Q4: In table 2, what is trait 1 and trait 2? Is trait 1=mealiness? And trait 2=softness?

Q5: In sampling strategy (section 3): please freeze-dry the cubes/slices intact (steps 3 and 6), no homogenisation is required at this stage and send to RHUL as freeze-dried pieces. At RHUL tissue will be ground to powder and prepared for metabolomics analysis.